

Original article

A study of clinical profile of stroke patients from Prime Medical College Hospital, Rangpur

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: Being the third most common cause of death and an important cause of morbidity, stroke has gained attention of researchers worldwide. For the past few decades, in concordance with the global trend, stroke incidence in our country has risen alarmingly. **OBJECTIVE:** The objective of the current work was to study patient profile, clinical presentation and neurological type of stroke in patients admitted in Prime Medical College Hospital. **METHOD:** This was a retrospective study using information of patients admitted with and managed for stroke in Medicine ward from July, 2014 to June, 2015. **RESULT:** Most of the stroke patients were in the age group of 51-70 years. Commonest type of stroke was ischemic (55.6%), Proportion of haemorrhagic stroke was greater (37%) in the current study in comparison to other studies, overall male were the predominant sufferer (63.5%) and weakness was the commonest presentation. **CONCLUSION:** More research on stroke should be carried out to improve patient care and clinical outcome.

KEY WORDS: Stroke, haemorrhagic stroke.

INTRODUCTION

With the advancement of medical science, longevity of human race has increased substantially. According to Bangladesh Bureau of statistics 2015 report, Current life expectancy of Bangladeshi people at birth is 70.4 years. The major difference in health concerns of past and present is that, we are now overwhelmed with the rising number of people suffering from so called “Non communicable disease (NCD)”. Among all other NCD’s stroke is a major burden globally. Stroke is defined by WHO as rapidly developed clinical signs of focal disturbance of

cerebral function lasting for more than 24 hours or leading to death without any apparent cause other than vascular origin¹. One study revealed that, stroke is the third leading cause of death in adult Bangladeshi². The mortality rate of stroke has increased from 6 % (in 2006) to 8.57%, (in 2011) and the age-adjusted mortality rate was found 108.31 per 100 000 people (in 2011)³.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This is a retrospective study on 151 patients with stroke who were admitted and managed in the department of Medicine during the tenure of July, 2014 to June, 2015. Information was collected from medical record keeping section of Department of Medicine. All patients with stroke who were more than 18 years were included. Patients who were below 18 years, without Computed tomography (CT) confirmation of stroke or had epidural or sub-dural haemorrhage were excluded from the study. Necessary data were extracted and analyzed with IBM SPSS 20.0 software.

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RESULTS

Most stroke patients were in the age group of 51-70 years (Table I and Figure 1).

Table I: Age distribution of patients (n= 151)

Age (Years)	Ischemic stroke	Haemorrhagic stroke	SAH
21-30	1(0.66)*	1(0.66)	1(0.66)
31-40	10(6.62)	2(1.32)	2(1.32)
41-50	9(5.9)	13(8.6)	1(0.66)
51-60	23(15.23)	20(13.24)	3(1.9)
61-70	23(15.23)	13(8.6)	2(1.32)
>70	18(11.9)	7(4.6)	2(1.32)

The figure in the parenthesis indicates percentage. SAH=sub-aracnoid haemorrhage

Figure 1: Age distribution of in different stroke patients

The mean age (\pm SD) for ischemic stroke was highest (61.57 ± 14.4) and it was lowest in sub-archnoid haemorrhage (SAH) (48.9 ± 21.02). Mean age for haemorrhagic stroke was in between these two (58.34 ± 12.2). The differences of these mean age were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$). (Table II).

Table II: Mean Age in different stroke

Types	Mean age	P value
Ischemic	61.57 ± 14.4	< 0.05
Haemorrhagic	58.34 ± 12.2	< 0.05
SAH	48.9 ± 21.02	< 0.05

SAH=sub-aracnoid haemorrhage

Ischemic stroke was the commonest type found in our study (55.6%) while SAH cases were least in number (7.28%) and haemorrhagic stroke cases were in between these two (37%). Among all the types of stroke, male preponderance was observed (male 63.5% and female 36.4%, M:F of 1.74:1), although in case of SAH patients of both sex were almost equally affected (Male 4% and Female 3.3%). Male patients were significantly ($P < 0.05$) more affected by ischemic and haemorrhagic stroke than female but this difference was not statistically significant ($P > 0.05$) in SAH patients (Table III and Figure 2).

Table III: Gender distribution of stroke patient (n= 151)

Type of stroke	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)	P Value
Ischemic	52(34.4)*	32(21.2)	84(55.6)	<0.005
Haemorrhagic	38(25.1)	18(12)	56(37)	<0.05
SAH	6(4)	5(3.3)	11(7.28)	0.9
Total	96(63.5)	55(36.4)	151	

*Figures in parenthesis indicates percentage

Figure 2: proportion of stroke in male and female

The leading presentation in ischemic stroke was weakness (66.6%) followed by altered level of consciousness (38%) and dysarthria (35.7%). Weakness was the commonest presentation in haemorrhagic stroke (73.2%) followed by vom-

iting(42.8%). In SAH, altered level of consciousness was the dominant symptom (54.5%) followed by headache, vomiting and weakness with almost same frequency (36.3%) (Table IV).

Table IV: Clinical presentation of stroke (n= 151)

Presenting complaints	Ischemic stroke (%)	Haemorrhagic stroke (%)	SAH (%)
Weakness	56(66.6)*	41(73.2)	4(36.3)
Altered consciousness	32(38)	20(35.7)	6(54.5)
Dysarthria	30(35.7)	16(28.5)	1(9)
Vomiting	17(20.2)	24(42.8)	4(36.3)
Headache	1(1.2)	1(1.8)	4(36.3)
convulsion	1(1.2)	1(1.8)	0(0)

*Figures in parenthesis indicates percentage. SAH=sub-aracnoid haemorrhage

The number of total patients admitted in the Department of Medicine during the study period was 3,069. Out of this, 151 (4.92%) patients were clinically diagnosed and confirmed by CT scan as stroke (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Proportion of stroke patients in Medicine Department in a year

Mean duration of hospital stay was highest among patients with SAH (6.7 d) that was close to the ischemic group (6 d) and in case of haemorrhagic stroke it was a bit shorter (4.3 d) (Table V and Figure 4).

Table V: Mean duration of stay at hospital (n= 151)

Type of stroke	Days
Ischemic	6
Haemorrhagic	4.3
SAH	6.7

Figure 4: Days of hospital stay in different stroke

DISCUSSION

According to an estimate of World Health Organization (WHO), 86% of all stroke related death occurs in developing countries⁴. In another study it was shown that, in south East Asian countries stroke occurs on an average 10 years earlier than the rest of the world⁵. Again, cardio-embolic stroke are less frequent in Asian countries than the Western side^{6,7,8}.

In the current study, we have found that male patients are affected by stroke more (63.5%) than female (36.4%) with a M:F of 1.74:1. This finding was similar to the finding of a study done in Faridpur medical college Hospital⁹ but differs from a study done by Alamgir et. al.¹⁰ and several studies done in Pakistan as they showed female preponderance^{11,12,13}. The male preponderance may be due to the presence of more risk factors for stroke like smoking in male than female. The current study showed that, male were significantly more affected than female by ischemic and haemorrhagic stroke but this difference was statistically insignificant in SAH. In our study, most of the stroke cases were ischemic (55.6%). Similar results were found by previous studies done on stroke in Bangladesh¹⁴. Although number of haemorrhagic stroke was lower (37%) than ischemic stroke (55.6%) in our study, but this proportion of haemorrhagic stroke was higher than haemorrhagic stroke in most of the Bangladeshi studies^{9,14}. This difference can be explained by the less devastating clinical picture of ischemic stroke that might have lead to less hospital admissions. The current study shows that, most vulnerable age group was 51-70 years, which was similar to the finding of studies of Dhaka and Faridpur Medical College Hospita^{19,14}. Weakness was the dominant presenting feature among ischemic and haemorrhagic stroke patients, whereas, altered level of consciousness was the main presenting feature in SAH (54.5%). Altered level of consciousness and headache were found in higher proportion in patients with SAH than the other types.

In our study we observed that, in proportion to the total admitted patients in the Department of Medicine, stroke covered a substantial number (4.92%). Our result is similar to a study done in Nigeria by Desalu et. al.¹⁵ where they have reported 4.5% stroke out of total Medicine admission. In contrast, a study done in Dhaka Medical College Hospital (DMCH) showed higher proportion (14%) of stroke admission¹⁶ which may be due to regional variation.

Mean duration of hospital stay was highest among patients with SAH (6.7 days) followed by Ischemic (6 days) and haemorrhagic (4.3 days). Regarding ischemic stroke, our result was compatible to that of a study done in USA¹⁷ where they have reported mean hospital stay of 6.5 days. The reason behind the short hospital stay of stroke patients in our country may be due to the lack of awareness as well as non-compliance of patients to continue in-hospital treatment. For the shorter stay of haemorrhagic patients in our study, referral of patients to other specialized centers for intervention might have played a role.

CONCLUSION

Once happened, stroke has a great toll on quality of life and major economic impact. Thus primary preventive strategy remains the best possible option to overcome the situation. Risk factor identification and control is of utmost importance. More research should be done on stroke in Bangladesh targeting primary prevention strategy and comprehensive stroke unit providing rehabilitation facility should be made available in tertiary care hospitals with a plan to extend the facility to District level hospitals.

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